

ALGAE FROM WASTE TO SUSTAINABLE VINEYARD RESOURCE

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Abstract

Sustainability is gaining increasing importance in many industrial sectors, and that includes the wine industry. Producers and operators in this sector recognize the importance of adopting sustainable practices not only with the aim of environmental preservation, but also for responsible resource management. Adopting environmentally friendly strategies that can reduce the use of known and accepted traditional synthetic pesticides and fertilizers needs to become a priority in the race for a cleaner and safer wine policy. This concept has applications not only for sustainability and circular economy purposes but also addresses EU consumer food safety standards. The present study aims to review the main techniques that use algae to enhance soil properties and generally the health of the vineyard, respecting the principles of the circular bioeconomy.

Introduction

Since the Industrial Revolution, the agriculture sector has become the primary source responsible for environmental change. A flawed relationship between humans and natural habitats developed, leading to negative consequences such as biodiversity loss and a never-before global climate crisis [1]. Current linear economic systems have enabled societies to prosper, while simultaneously exploiting planetary resources (i.e., raw materials) and primary energy (i.e., fossil fuels) at an exponential rate, with the mismanagement of limited natural resources. All forms of capital rely on non-substitutable natural capital. Present economic concepts focus on sustainable use of resources, and that “we received this world as an inheritance from past generations, but also as a loan from future generations” [2].

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The sustainability principle of circular economy translates as an attempt at minimising the impact of human activities on natural environments, human health, and natural resources [3]. Transitioning from our current linear economy to a circular one is one possible option that can balance our use of finite natural resources while making our economic system more resilient. Circular economy tries to reduce the dependency on (new) natural resource extraction while increasing the time resources spend within the technological chain through alternate use cycles. Often circular economy can be complemented by bioeconomy, a concept that can incorporate economic activities related to the invention, development, production, and use of biological products and processes for energy, materials, and chemicals [4]. The resulting intersection can be referred to as “circular bioeconomy.” Although this intersection can potentially guide a transition to more sustainable production and consumption, the concept is still not fully understood, with many remaining challenges and research questions to be addressed. Currently, organizations and researchers define the concept differently, resulting in confusion and difficulty in effectively implementing the framework. Additionally, terms like “circular bioeconomy” and “sustainability” are frequently and incorrectly interchanged in academia, industry, and policymaking.

There are over 100 definitions of circular economy [5],[6],[7],[8],[9],[10]. The concept of circular economy is understood and has been subjectively to the scientific community and decision factors. Gallie (1956) summarised the concept in which there is agreement on the means and goals of the concept but disagreements on how it is defined (Korhonen, 2018).

Bioeconomy as an emerging field focusing on economic strategies, concepts that use renewable resources to produce foods, raw materials, and energy (European Commission Research Innovation Bioeconomy (ECRIB, 2019), [11].

Transition from a fossil-based to biomass-based industrial inputs that emphasizes the sustainable use of renewable resources for economic, environmental, and social benefits can only be obtained by the way of bioeconomy concepts [12], [13], [14]. In the case of biodegradable bioplastics, up to 90% of the organic carbon can be converted to CO₂ in about 180 days; CO₂ carbon form can only return to the biosphere after passing through a use phase [15].

Circular bioeconomy represents the merger of two concepts defined by circular economy and bioeconomy. The relationship between the circular economy and bioeconomy is rather complex. Bioeconomy refers to circular bioeconomy as being the backbone for this concept that reduces dependency on natural resources; transforms industrial processes; promotes sustainable production via the use of renewable resources while developing and sustaining new jobs and industries [16]. A circular bioeconomy is also interpreted as an idea to stimulate economic growth that combines the desirable with the feasible and viable [17].

The present study aims to review the main techniques that use algae to enhance soil properties and generally the health of the vineyard, respecting the principles of the circular bioeconomy.

Materials and Methods

Scientific literature was consulted using the main scientific databases: *Google Scholar*, *Science Direct*, and *Elsevier*.

The timeline for scientific literature selection was focused on the 2013-2025 interval. Keywords of the research were in line with our scientific aim.

Results and Discussions

Sustainability aspects

Vine cultivation is an important economic sector in global agriculture and a cultural legacy in many regions around the world [18]. Vineyard ecosystems are particularly endangered because the soil function is often compromised by agricultural practices, repeated over time, for pest and weed management that are applied intensively and can have harmful effects [19]. In the European region, vineyards are identified as the most vulnerable areas subjected to the highest runoff and soil losses, which might lead to a reduction in the quality of the grapes and wine, especially because of the soil organic matter loss [20],[21]. Preservation strategies need to be adapted to new sustainable alternatives in this sector without compromising the production yields [22]. The use of seaweeds can become such an alternative. This natural resource could offer a sustainable and cost-effective solution in contrast to traditional mineral fertilizing due to the frequent proximity of vineyards to coastal areas. Making use of drifting seaweed biomass that is often present along tourist seaside venues would allow local municipalities to resolve a common economic and environmental problem and turn it into a circular bioeconomy strategy [23].

Seaweed suitability as a raw source in composting strategies and natural fertilizer was proven by numerous scientific studies that showed positive results regarding soil quality and fertility parameters due to soil microbiota stimulation [24]. Seaweed use as a soil amendment tool is gaining momentum in the sustainable agriculture game because of crop biomass increases, yield improvements, fruit quality, and resistance to biotic and abiotic stressors when used [25],[26]. Seaweed compost, in addition, might improve water and nutrient retention by delivering bioactive substances like vitamins, minerals, growth regulators, and organic compounds to the soil medium [27], [28]. The reported agronomic impact varied according to the algae species employed and the condition of the substrate where the applications were carried out [29]. Seaweed components will reflect crop yields and results of the presence of soil health parameters [30], [31]. In fact, they have been particularly useful under stress conditions, for example, drought and salinity, which are of vital importance [32].

The soils that received treatment showed notable enhancements, indicating increased nitrogen levels and suggesting that composted seaweed can efficiently maintain and even slightly enhance soil nitrogen retention, thereby promoting long-term soil health and fertility without adverse effects on productivity [33]. Strategies that use animal organic matter and seaweed compost registered better results on soil total nitrogen ratios when compared to inorganic fertilization, which was attributed to the clear increase of SOM [32]. Available K values were directly linked to seaweed ratios due to the general, natural high K content in algae [34]. High soil K levels can have detrimental effects on wine quality with a resulting high pH value, and they can also directly affect cluster number, weight, and consequently grape yield, which can be taken into consideration [35]. High concentrations of macroelements (N, P, K, Ca) and microelements such as Mg, together with essential amino acids and hormones, represent the primary nutrient source for healthy plant growth, which coincides with seaweed characteristics, resulting in significant nutrient content increases, with an overall higher yield. The modifying effect on soil characteristics boosts mineral uptake, growth on both roots, yield, and biomass density [36].

Additional heavy metal presence

In seaweed compost, we see some potential for accumulating heavy metals [37]. Heavy metal contamination was below the LOQ established by the EU policy makers (Commission

Decision (EU) 2015/2099) when the algae source was non-contaminated [33]. In this regard, element analysis is mandatory before composting, as metal and heavy metal concentrations in seaweed compost are directly related to seaweed species and their surrounding environment [38]. Based on the potential algae taxonomy characteristics isn't sufficient information for heavy metals accumulation rates [39]. Cd, Mn, or Ni tended to increase over time, suggesting that their turnover rate is significantly slower compared to other inorganic elements, and their release/uptake must be monitored if recurrent use of the compost is desired. Studies show that metal removal from the surrounding environment specific to seaweed biomass, is related to the particular biosorption strength attributed to seaweed cell walls that interact with metal ions differently.

Besides their natural biosorbent role for heavy metals, their favorable effects on agriculture as an alternative to conventional fertilizers have been empirically proven since the early industrial age [40],[41]. Vineyard uses showed beneficial effects ranging from early fruit ripening, higher number of grapes per plant, larger berry size and weight, and phenolic compound increases [42],[43].

The limitations of seaweed compost use are apparent due to the tendency of C/N ratios to be unbalanced, resulting in vegetative growth limitations when compost techniques over use were implemented [44]. Results presented by Cole (2016), in which seaweed compost of maximum concentration of 20% maintained an optimum C/N ratio, avoiding the mentioned limitations, and obtained better yields [45].

Economic perspectives

Composting biodegradable waste offers multiple economic advantages [46]. Composting programs can lead to significant cost savings for municipalities by reducing the need for landfill space and the costs associated with organic waste collection and disposal [47]. For the agricultural sector, including viticulture, compost represents a cost-effective, sustainable substitute with the potential to lower input costs [48],[49]. As composting initiatives expand, they create job opportunities in collection, processing, and distribution, stimulating local economies, supporting job growth in the circular bioeconomy sector [50]. Circular bioeconomy programs produced in Minnesota [51] approximately 700 jobs and contributed an estimated USD 148 million to the state's economy. Another case study reported an additional 1400 new full-time jobs in Maryland, paying wages ranging from USD 23 million to USD 57 million related to organic compost production [52]. According to data available from the Iowa Department of Natural Resources, using compostable materials from landfills could save nearly USD 100 million, and save nearly 1.5 million tons of landfill space, with over 19,000 jobs generated and substantial revenue supplement [53].

Compost shows great export potential, especially as the demand for organic agricultural products is on the rise at a global level [54]. Over 1.3 billion tons of biodegradable waste are generated each year [55]. At the same time, most countries face challenges in composting this biodegradable waste due to logistical deficiencies and large-scale agricultural production. Research on biodegradable waste exhibits a mixed approach, as progressive states make significant advances in this area while underdeveloped countries lag due to legislative void and lack of infrastructure. From a global landscape perspective, it can be observed the a need for a standardized waste management strategy that addresses the diverse sources and quantities of biodegradable waste effectively [56].

Composting initiatives' long-term success and scalability are dependent on governmental policies that support and promote the circular use of compost. There are several financial tools (tax breaks, grants, and low-interest loans) that can reduce initial costs for composting operations, making them feasible for private companies and individual farmers.

Subsidizing programs that include compost use as an objective for urban parks and garden community projects can encourage widespread adoption of these types of practices. A simple and clear regulatory framework is essential for compost quality parameters, contamination prevention, and standardized processing methods [57]. Organic waste separation and extended producer responsibility programs can assist and increase composting efficiency, promoting compostable packaging, resulting in minimal waste contamination. Partnerships that include public and private partners are crucial in infrastructure development to extend composting program access to rural and isolated regions. Sustainable agricultural practices that focus on compost use in farming, erosion control, and carbon sequestration while reducing greenhouse gas emissions can be encouraged via governmental subsidies [58], [59].

Conclusions

Our current review highlights the potential of seaweed organic potential to maintain soil fertility for multiannual crops and meet vine nutrient requirements. Resulting materials from composting seaweed are suitable organic amendments for agricultural use in vineyards, adding an agronomic value to a bioresource that otherwise will turn into a residue. There are reports that seaweed compost is responsible for C/N ratio amendment, with some risks of higher than needed physiological concentrations. Also, the natural ability of seaweed to absorb heavy metal species could limit the use of this kind of organic source. As presented in our review research, analytical testing for trace amounts of heavy metals is mandatory for this type of organic waste. Unbalanced C/N ratios and unspecific heavy metal accumulation should be closely monitored in order to adapt composting applications for optimal yield. General economic advantages are evident in areas that concern waste reduction, cost savings in waste disposal, job creation, and the need for expensive synthetic fertilizers. Composting practices play a vital role within the circular bioeconomy, fostering innovation and contributing to the sustainability of the natural ecosystem through reduced methane emissions and improved soil health. The benefits of a sustainable and regenerative waste management system are able to generate long-term economic and environmental returns.

Initial challenges, such as initial costs for setting up composting infrastructure, the need for organic matter quality control and standards, market competition with chemical fertilizers, and limited awareness in the private sector, remain key barriers.

Promotion of eco-friendly management of marine by-products remains essential in the context of the climate challenge, helping to reduce the reliance on traditional mineral or oil-derived fertilizers, and achieving the EU legislative reduction target of 10% by 2030.

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